

INDIVIDUAL-TYOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS AS ADAPTATION OF YOUNG ATHLETES TO SPORTS ACTIVITY

Jalolova.Z.S

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University social and humanitarian sciences
teacher of the department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7315828>

Abstract. *In this article, it is highlighted that social factors and, most importantly, individual characteristics are important in the adaptation of young athletes to sports activities.*

Key words: *sport, psychology, individuality, temperament, adolescent.*

ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНО-ТИПОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ КАК АДАПТАЦИЯ ЮНЫХ СПОРТСМЕНОВ К СПОРТИВНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье подчеркивается, что в адаптации юных спортсменов к спортивной деятельности важное значение имеют социальные факторы и, главное, индивидуальные особенности.*

Ключевые слова: *спорт, психология, индивидуальность, темперамент, подросток.*

INTRODUCTION

In sports activities, the mental world of the athlete consists of a continuous set of activities, one of which directly requires the other, and they rule in a way similar to a continuous chain system. For the same reason, impressions of the external environment, memories of the past, creative imaginations about the future, good intentions, desires, goals and wishes, reasoning, thoughts and problems, emotional experiences, volitional qualities are present in the psyche of a young athlete. due to their continuous interchange, a solid foundation is prepared for the ontogenetic world. It is observed that the passage of the spiritual world, its speed, content, scope of form, characteristic, character, quality, and mechanism are manifested in different ways in a single person. That's probably why people tend to respond quickly or slowly, easily or with difficulty to natural phenomena, factors, influence forces.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

In the adaptation of young athletes to sports activities, the individuality and character of the teenager are of great importance. Because a teenager reacts to external influences more or less relying on the experience he has gained in life, and at the same time accelerates the process of adaptation to the environment in which he lives and to the sports field, which has become a certain part of his activities. An athlete 's temperament plays an important role in his adaptation to sports circles. It should be emphasized that adaptation of athletes to sports circles is directly related not only to temperament, but also to motives, mental states, and emotions. In psychology, it is emphasized that there is a certain degree of difference between individual dynamic characteristics related to temperament and dynamic characteristics of motives and psychological states, emotional experiences. In order to distinguish between them, additional symbols are introduced and described in a unique way. It is appropriate to highlight some of them. 1. The same characteristics of extraordinary temperament, in contrast to motive, mental state and events, are expressed in this person himself, in his various activities, behaviors, behavior.

2. Temperament characteristics are stable, unchanging, and stable throughout human life and activity (lifetime) or in a certain part of it (regardless of the reason for susceptibility to influence) due to the fact that they are related to the factor of natural conditioning.

3. The different characteristics of temperament characteristic of a single person are not combined with each other illegally, but they are mutually embodied on the basis of a certain law, and the same characteristics create a unique structure that characterizes his types.

4. Temperament characteristics in the science of psychology mean a set of stable, unchanging individual-typological characteristics of the psyche that determine the dynamics of the mental activity of a particular teenager. These characteristics form a relatively invariable structure describing the type of temperament in motives, mental states, goals, and activities with different forms and content.

Temperament and character are characteristics of an individual that are evident in social relationships. By character, we understand the individual features formed in a person under the influence of environment and education and manifested in his volitional activity, self-relation to the surrounding world (other people, work, things) . These psychological characteristics of adolescent sports athletes are manifested in concrete conditions. Concrete conditions are characterized depending on the development of each society. Sport is one of the most important activities of a person. Because a democratic society and concepts about this society cannot be imagined without physical abilities.

In sports, a person matures physically, and physical development affects the growth of mental qualities in a person. These two are organically connected and cannot be separated. Thus, a person is a natural being and has psychological characteristics. These characteristics mature in the course of the individual's activity. Sports Sports are one of the concrete, most important activities of a person. Therefore, sports are one of the means of personal development. Therefore, sport is of great importance in the comprehensive education of a person.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Sports require high speed and agility to exert maximum neuromuscular effort in order to achieve a discharge or set a record. Sport is distinguished from other types of human activity by its strength. In the process of sports, the movement skills of a teenager develop at a high level. Also, voluntary and other psychological qualities of a person improve in sports. In this period, the essence of engaging young people in one or another type of sports is that if a teenager spends the period of playing sports well, high physical ability, will and character will be cultivated, as well as a worldview will be formed. On the contrary, if a teenager is deprived of physically active games or does not play sports during this important period of growth, it will be difficult for him to rise to the level of a fully mature person in the course of his life.

So, playing sports during a certain period of the growth process in a teenager educates the most important physical qualities for future life: agility, dexterity, courage, physical beauty and other important qualities. When an athlete engages in one or another type of sport, he always aims to achieve high results . And this from a teenage athlete:

- As a result of long-term training, it requires general physical development, highly developed physiological functions of the body.

- Thinking in an athlete requires a high degree of operationalization. Because in sports, there are often issues related to methods and tactics that require immediate resolution. This necessity develops the ability to think in sports. In addition, emotions, perception and other mental processes mature in sports.

•The results of scientific investigations show that sports play an important role in training the temperament and character of a sports person, and when examining coaches and athletes with many years of experience, it is rare for them to have an empty nervous system. However, people with an empty nervous system are often found among people who do not play sports.

•Phlegmatic-tempered person cannot run fast in close distance, and he cannot move fast in boxing, but it has been proved that such a change of the nervous system as a result of training can take over some sports.

•Choleric - temperamental people are very suitable for short-distance running and boxing, but they are very excited during the competition, they get angry quickly when overcoming obstacles. As can be seen from the above, the individual-typological characteristics of each young athlete are of great importance in the adaptation of athletes to sports activities. Based on this point of view, in the process of adaptation of young athletes to sports activities, it is appropriate to pay special attention to young people in each sport. In the adaptation of adolescent sportsmen to sports circles, the adolescent's family conditions, the main activities of his friends around him, upbringing in the family, the distance and proximity of the gym where he attends training, the location of the gym, the uniqueness of the coach and psychological knowledge. having, the main thing is related to his sincere love for the sports field he has chosen. The influence of social factors and individual-psychological characteristics on the teenager, education and the surrounding environment are of great importance in the adaptation of adolescent athletes to sports clubs . In conclusion, we think it is appropriate to point out the following.

•Sports are of particular importance in the harmonious development of the adolescent athlete.

•The mental processes of the adolescent sports athlete influence the improvement of sports activities, and sports, in turn, play the role of the main resource in the growth of this process at a high level.

•High results in sports cannot be achieved without the will-ideal qualities of a teenager. These qualities are formed in concrete sports conditions.

•Sport is a powerful source of positive change in a person's temperament. According to the successful adaptation of young athletes to the new professional activity in the environment of sports activities, the respondents are conditionally divided into the following three groups: 1) successful (successfully adapted to sports activities - those who have high results and are satisfied with the creative process in the new work activity)); 2) relatively successful (partially adapted to the process of their relationship to sports activities - those who have high labor productivity, but are not satisfied with the process of new activity(s); 3) unsuccessful (those who are not adapted to the new professional activity, have low productivity and are less satisfied with the activity) are divided into subjects of sports activities. The following are the main criteria for successful adaptation: a) high satisfaction with professional activity (generally accepted objective criteria); b) the number of jobs created by the labor entity (additional object criteria); c) reluctance of the athlete to change his professional activity in cases where he is offered a benefit for other sports activities (main subjective criteria); g) factors such as meaningful indicators of life (additional subjective indicators) are accepted. Thus, the study showed that 66 (45.1%) athletes formed a social group that showed a high level of adaptation to success. That is, when analyzing the activities of this category of respondents, their interest in sports increased due to

their foresight and proper planning of sports training . 17 (11.5%) test subjects belong to the social group consisting of unsuccessful sports subjects. It was found that their interest in sports activities has decreased or is insignificant, their participation in training has decreased as before, their satisfaction indicators are low, and they want to change their fields of activity and have not been able to adapt to this professional activity at all. Also, another 64 respondents who participated in the study belong to the group of relatively successful sports subjects. The results show that their participation in training has increased to a certain extent and their number has increased.

CONCLUSION

When conducting the pilot phase dedicated to the experimental study of the socio-psychological adaptation of young athletes to sports activities, it was considered appropriate to pay attention to the instructional recommendations that are followed in the study of experimental psychology and social thought at the maximum level. This was the basis for drawing the following scientific conclusions: –sports motives that cause the choice of sports activities and factors affecting personal adaptation in a changing environment, in particular, although a person cannot change the natural conditions, by forming a healthy psychological environment in the sports team, young athletes can be socialized even in unfavorable conditions - psychological adjustment can be increased; –socio-psychological adaptation to sports professional activity can be divided into five levels: lower, below average, middle, above average, and high levels, and these levels are: a) the state of entering into mutual relations; b) not to engage in long-term external and internal conflicts during sports activities; c) satisfaction of sociogenic needs; g) be prepared for role expectations that may be presented by society (sometimes a non-reference group); d) helps in determining whether one can demonstrate his creative abilities independently and confidently, and determines the extent of social-psychological adjustment.

REFERENCES

1. physical culture and sport: teacher for study. higher fly zavedeniy / G.D. Gorbunov, E.N. Gogunov. - M.: Izdatelsky center "Academy". 2009. – 256 p.
2. Gapparov Z.G. "Sports psychology". "Mekhridaryo" LLC, 2011.